

Studies on the Interfacial Tension and Electrical Conductance of Oil/Water Emulsions Stabilized by Lignosulphonate of *Eucalyptus teriticornis*

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Kerosene/water and turpentine/water emulsions stabilized by lignosulphonate have been prepared. Their interfacial tension and electrical conductance have been measured and discussed as a function of emulsifier concentration, temperature, salinity, alcohol-carbon chain length, emulsification time with temperature and phase volume ratio.

It is generally accepted that higher concentration of lignosulphonate, carbon chain length of alcohols and temperature lower the interfacial tension but increase the conductance and make the emulsions more conductive. Literature reveals that oil/water emulsions have been prepared by employing soaps¹, Indian gums², surfactants³, proteins⁴, saponins⁵ etc., as emulsifiers and their properties such as interfacial tension⁶, surface tension and viscosity⁷, particle size⁸, stability⁹, creaming¹⁰, phase inversion¹¹ etc. have also been studied. The effect of phase-volume ratio on the physico-chemical properties of oil/water emulsions, dielectric constants¹² etc. has also appeared in literature. In the present investigations attempts have been made to assess the emulsifying power of lignosulphonates, a waste product of paper industry, by measuring the interfacial tension and electrical properties of kerosene/water and turpentine/water emulsions stabilized by this product. A correlation of interfacial tension with the conductance of emulsions has also been made.

Experimental

Double distilled kerosene (sp. gr. 0.7948), turpentine (sp. gr. 0.8745) and water having conductance 1×10^{-5} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ were used in all the experiments. The alcohols viz., methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *n*-butanol, pentanol, and sodium chloride used were of B.D.H. AR grade. The lignosulphonate from eucalyptus wood was prepared at Star Paper Mill, Saharanpur and at Cellulose and Paper Branch, Forest Research Institute, Dehradun.

Preparation of emulsion and measurement of its conductance: Oil/water emulsions have been prepared by taking kerosene and turpentine as internal phase in the following manner:

1. Keeping the concentration of lignosulphonate constant (0.5%) and varying the oil/

water ratio viz., 10 : 10, 10 : 20, 10 : 30, 10 : 40, 10 : 50, 10 : 60, 10 : 70, 10 : 80 and 10 : 90.

2. Keeping the oil/water ratio (1 : 3) and concentration of lignosulphonate (0.5%) constant and varying the emulsification temperature viz., 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60° alongwith the emulsification time viz., 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and 12 min, respectively.
3. Keeping oil/water ratio (1 : 3) and the concentration of lignosulphonate (0.5%) constant and adding 0.1% of alcohols viz., methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *n*-butanol and pentanol.

Emulsions were prepared by agent-in-water method¹³ and the conductance was measured with a sensitive conductivity bridge instrument.

Measurements of interfacial tension: The interfacial tension of different concentration of lignosulphonate in water viz., 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08 and 0.1% and the salinity effect by adding different concentrations viz., 0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.08, 0.1, 0.12, 0.16, 0.20 and 0.24% of NaCl to 0.05% lignosulphonate solution, have been measured against kerosene and turpentine oils by drop-volume method^{14,15}, respectively.

The effect of various alcohols i.e. methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, *n*-butanol and pentanol on the interfacial tension of 0.05% aqueous solution of lignosulphonate against kerosene and turpentine have also been measured by keeping alcohol concentration constant (0.1% v/v) and calculated by

the equation:
$$\gamma_{ow} = \frac{V(d_1 - d_2)g \times F}{r}$$
 where, γ_{ow}

is the interfacial tension, V the volume of single drop, d_1 and d_2 the densities of respective phases, g the gravity, r the radius of the dropping tip and F is the correction factor¹⁶. All the results have been presented in Figs. 1 to 4 and Tables 1 to 5.

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE INTERFACIAL TENSION OF OIL/0.05% AQ SOLUTION OF LIGNOSULPHONATE

Temp. °C	Interfacial tension (Dynes/cm)	
	Kerosene/water	Turpentine/ water
20	11.24	8.58
25	10.99	8.43
30	10.83	8.13
35	10.50	7.98
40	10.18	7.78

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PHASE-VOLUME RATIO ON THE CONDUCTANCE OF O/W EMULSIONS

Lignosulphonate=0.5% ; Temp. = 25 ± 1°

O/W Ratio	Conductance × 10 ⁻³ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
	Turpentine/water	Kerosene/water
10 : 10	5.68	3.47
10 : 20	7.80	4.80
10 : 30	8.92	5.47
10 : 40	10.98	6.38
10 : 50	12.40	7.40
10 : 60	14.10	8.44
10 : 70	16.80	8.97
10 : 80	17.92	9.74
10 : 90	18.05	10.59

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF EMULSIFICATION TEMPERATURE AND TEMPERATURE ON THE CONDUCTANCE OF O/W EMULSIONS

O/W Ratio=1 : 3 ; Lignosulphonate concn : 0.5%

Temp. °C	Emulsification effect		Temperature effect	
	Conductance × 10 ⁻³ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹		Conductance × 10 ⁻³ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
	Kerosene/water	Turpentine/water	Kerosene/water	Turpentine/water
20	9.04	14.2	8.53	11.80
30	9.58	14.8	12.62	14.85
40	9.89	15.1	14.51	16.02
50	10.20	15.7	16.39	17.7
60	10.83	16.3	17.80	19.1

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ALCOHOL CARBON CHAIN LENGTH ON THE CONDUCTANCE OF O/W EMULSIONS

Lignosulphonate concn : 0.5% ; O/W Ratio 1 : 3 ; Alcohol 0.1%

Alcohol	Conductance × 10 ⁻³ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
	Kerosene/water	Turpentine/water
CH ₃ OH	11.70	15.2
C ₂ H ₅ OH	11.74	15.4
n-C ₃ H ₇ OH	11.79	15.8
n-C ₄ H ₉ OH	11.81	15.95
C ₆ H ₁₁ OH	11.85	16.05
C ₈ H ₁₇ OH	11.89	16.3

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF EMULSIFICATION TIME ON THE CONDUCTANCE OF O/W EMULSIONS

O/W Ratio 1 : 3 ; Lignosulphonate=0.5% ; Temp. = 25 ± 1°

Emulsification time (min)	Conductance × 10 ⁻³ ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
	Kerosene/water	Turpentine/water
0.5	10.05	13.8
1.0	10.69	14.2
2.0	10.91	14.9
4.0	11.34	16.5
8.0	12.56	18.3
12.0	12.57	18.31

Results and Discussion

The interfacial tension of kerosene/water and turpentine/water interfaces against varying concentrations of lignosulphonate (Fig. 1) depict a

Fig. 1. Effect of lignosulphonate concentration on the interfacial tension of oil/water emulsions.

decrease in surface tension of emulsions with an increase in lignosulphonate concentration. In both the cases, the decrease is linear at concentration 0.08% and beyond. This lowering of interfacial tension is attributed to the adsorption of lignosulphonate at oil/water interface and as adsorption reaches a constant value due to the formation of monolayer, the lowering in interfacial tension becomes smaller and smaller¹⁷.

Fig. 2 indicates a decrease in the interfacial tension of oil/water emulsion with an increase in

Fig. 2. Effect of alcohol carbon chain length on the interfacial tension of oil/water emulsions.

the carbon chain of alcohol. A break is observed in passing from *n*-propanol to *n*-butanol. This is expected as less soluble alcohols (in water) solubilize more oil and consequently lower the interfacial tension¹⁹. Fig. 3 shows the rise and fall in interfacial tension with increasing sodium chloride

while Table 2 indicates a fall in the conductance of emulsion with increasing phase-volume ratio. This may be attributed to an increase in the number of droplets with the increase in phase-volume ratio.

At higher emulsifier temperature the emulsions appear to be more conducting (Table 3). However,

Fig. 3. Effect of salinity on the interfacial tension of oil/water emulsions.

concentration. The temperature shows an adverse effect on interfacial tension, the decrease being linear with rise of temperature. This is in harmony with the results of earlier workers¹⁹.

It is clear from Fig. 4 that conductance increases with an increase in the concentration of emulsifier,

in some cases, emulsions first prepared at room temperature show an increase in conductance in the temperature range 20° to 60°. This may be due to an increase in the mobility of oil-droplets.

Tables 4 and 5 present the effect of alcohol carbon-chain and emulsification time on the conductance of kerosene/water and turpentine/water emulsions. It is evident that as the carbon chain of alcohols and emulsification time increase, the conductance of emulsions also increases. It can thus be concluded that emulsions having lower interfacial tension show higher conductance values.

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References

- (Miss) PRATIMA ACHARYA and TRILOK CHAND, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 730.
- L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 177.
- P. K. SHARMA and TRILOK CHAND, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1206.
- TRILOK CHAND, *Rak. J. Sci. Res.*, 1979, **31**, 291.

Fig. 4. Effect of lignosulphonate concn. on conductance of oil/water emulsions.

5. E. K. NEOGY and B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958 **30**, 113.
6. H. D. TAYAL and TRILOK CHAND, *J. Collod and Polym. Sci.*, 1979, **257**, 1125
7. K. D. JAIN and M. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 779.
8. TRILOK CHAND and (Miss) PRATIMA ACHARYA, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1980 **6**, 217.
9. TRILOK CHAND, *J. Collod and Polym. Sci.*, 1980 **258**, 1204.
10. TRILOK CHAND, (Miss) PRATIMA ACHARYA and P. K. SHARMA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1979, 38.
11. P. SHERMAN, *Research (London)*, 1955, **8**, 396.
12. TRILOK CHAND and P. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 85.
13. P. BECHERE, "Emulsion, Theory and Practice", Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1966, p. 267.
14. E. MATIJEVIC and B. A. PETHICA, *Croat. Chem. Acta* 1957, **29**, 43.
15. H. C. PERRIERA, *J. Collod Sci.*, 1965, **20**, 44.
16. W. D. HARKINS and F. E. BROWN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1919, **41**, 499.
17. TRILOK CHAND, *Egypt J. Chem.*, 1979, **22**, 281.
18. T. MITSUI, S. NAKAMURA, F. HARUSAWA and Y. MACHIDA, *Kolloid Z. Z. Polymere*, 1972, **250**, 227.